

African Union's Role in the Promotion of Good Governance and Political Development in Nigeria

Abstract

The African Union (AU) has been pursuing one of its primary objectives of promoting democratic principles and institutions by ensuring good governance through the curbing of corruption, ensuring free and fair elections through monitoring of elections in order to ensure sustainable political development. It is uncertain whether the democratic approach has rubbed off on its anti-corruption initiatives, given the recent performance of most AU member states especially Nigeria on many global surveys of corruption, development and governance evaluation indexes. The paper, therefore, examined the extent to which the AU's stance on democratic promotion has impacted on political development in Nigeria. The integration theory was adopted as the framework of analysis for the paper. The paper is both qualitative and quantitative which relied on data sourced from questionnaires and interviews as well as secondary sources, while content analysis was adopted for data analysis. The findings acknowledged AU's efforts in promoting political development in Nigeria through its different anti-corruption and election monitoring frameworks. But in spite of the slight improvements of Nigeria on different corruption perception indexes, and fragile democratic system, corruption and electoral fraud still persists in the governance of Nigeria and many AU member states. The paper further shows inter alia that the AU's anti-corruption initiatives have not effectively reflected the adopted measures due to uncommon democratic practices in Nigeria. The paper contended that Nigerian government in collaboration with African Union should endeavour to uphold democracy in its purest form in order to ensure and sustain political development in the country

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Introduction

The trajectory of African development since its decade of independence tends to be a contradictory admixture of hope and despair. Undoubtedly, political independence came with great expectations which were hinged on the dialectical permutation that the collapse of colonialism would usher in an epoch of unhindered national development. But that hope was quickly transformed into despair as African states became embroiled in all manner of socio-economic and political contradictions, thus occupying the “bottom of global development and poverty scale, with human conditions largely moving backwards” (Odukoya, 2018). The early attempt at institutionalising African unity was under the auspices of the Organisation of African unity (OAU) (now African Union, AU). Scholars are of the opinion that OAU was successful in actualizing the dismantling of colonialism and apartheid but ineffective in motorising the integration of African states and steering them to sustainable development (Nwozor, 2018).

Nigeria's neo-conservatism and commitment to promoting a democratic ethos in Africa have been subsumed under certain guidelines, under the Constitutive Act of the AU. Among these are, on the one hand, a strong repudiation of unconstitutional changes of governments, and, on the other hand, financial and technical assistance to transitional states, and a commitment to peace and conflict management in Africa (Bakare, 2019).

On the other hand, the African Union (AU) has affirmed its seven

aspirations for the future of the African continent through the “Agenda 2063: The Africa We Want” framework (Agenda 2063), which was adopted in 2015.1 Aspiration 4 of Agenda 2063 is “a peaceful and secure Africa”, and the goals for this aspiration are “preservation of peace, security and stability” (goal 13), “a stable and peaceful Africa” (goal 14), and “a fully functional peace and security architecture” (goal 15). It is significant that the AU included Aspiration 4 in Agenda 2063, in view of the scourge of conflicts and unconstitutional changes of government (UCG) through military coups, all of which have a detrimental effect on the socio-economic development of the continent (Mushoriwa, 2023).

There is no iota of doubt that Nigeria has made significant contributions towards the emergence, development and sustainability of African Union. Nevertheless, it cannot be debunked that the AU in its own capacity as a regional organization has also made a significant contribution in the political development of Nigeria through various ways such as electoral observation to ensure free fair and credible election, human rights policies and anticorruption policies as highlighted in the subsequent section of this paper.

Since the transition from the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) to the African Union (AU) on 9 July 2002, several governance institutions and mechanisms have been devised to accelerate democratic development and socio-economic good governance in Africa. These commitments are spelt out not only in the AU Constitutive Act itself, but also in the declaration on

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unconstitutional changes of government; the declaration governing democratic elections; and the declaration on observing and monitoring elections. The institutionalisation of these instruments suggests that African leaders have come to attach a reasonable measure of importance to democracy and good political governance as prerequisites for the development and stability of Africa (Omotola, 2014). It is against this backdrop that this paper is set out to investigate the African Union and the promotion of good governance and enhancement of political development in Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What is the role of African Union in Promoting good governance in Nigeria?
- ii. What impact do African Union's policies and initiatives have on the fight against corruption in Nigeria?

Research Objectives

- i. To examine the role of the African Union in promoting good governance in Nigeria.
- ii. To assess the impact of the African Union's policies and initiatives on the fight against corruption in Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Ayodeji, Kolade, and Abiodun, (2023), carried out a paper on African Union, Promotion of Democracy and Anti-Corruption Initiatives in Africa. The paper is qualitative and relied on data sourced from secondary sources, while content analysis was adopted for data analysis. The findings acknowledge AU's committed advancement of

democracy in Africa through its different anti-corruption frameworks. But in spite of the slight improvements of some African counties on different corruption perception indexes, corruption persists in the governance of many AU member states. The paper contends that AU's anti-corruption bodies should ensure and encourage member states to internalise and uphold existing governance norms and accountability measures, while implementation mechanisms should be strengthened.

Mustapha (2020), in a paper on Nigeria and the African Union (2002–2019) the qualitative and descriptive historical methods were adopted in analyzing the primary sources. The paper employed the role theory to reveal, develop, and validate the correlation between the role of Nigeria in the African Union and in the regional integration for economic and political realization. The paper therefore recommends among others that the regionalization of economic activities will enable national economies to build capacities in all critical areas via the absorption and generation of new production and marketing technologies as a starting point for a more meaningful participation in the world economy.

Umezurike, Iwu, Asuelime, and Umezurike (2017), empirically investigated the phenomenon of re-examining Nigeria's contributions to the African Union and the domestic socio-economic ramifications. This paper depended on a desk-top review of secondary data and documentary analysis methodology in the review where it was found that there is a serious misalignment between Nigeria's

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diplomacy and support for the African Union on one hand and positive socio-economic development in Nigeria on the other. While there have been scholarly studies that address Nigeria's diplomacy and contribution to the African Union (AU), many of them have failed to compare and contrast how those have added to the socio-economic development of Nigeria. The paper concludes that Nigeria has not been able to transform its role under AU to its national benefit, therefore, the paper recommends among others that for Nigeria's role in the AU to be meaningful, the country needs to simultaneously revive its internal socio-economic condition.

Aniekwe & Atuobi (2016), did a paper on two decades of election observation by the African Union: A Review. The paper utilized the secondary source of data collection and content method of analysis. The paper observed that between 1989 and 2013, the African Union (AU) observed 423 elections in Africa. However, these election observation missions were inconsistent at best in terms of approach, methodology, framework and status. The first, which was in Namibia in 1989, was deployed within the framework of the United Nations (UN) statute in terms of which the UN invited the AU. The subsequent election observation missions have to date been deployed either as diplomatic or mediation missions or a combination of diplomatic and independent technical missions.

This article shows that the election observation journey of the AU has passed through several stages and regimes. While we recognise the challenges, we also point towards improvement, and identify the missing

links by recommending that the AU needs to complete to become a truly independent actor in its election observation missions.

Theoretical Framework

Integration Theory

International integration refers to the process by which supernatural institutions replace national ones-the gradual shifting upward of sovereignty from state to regional or global structures. The ultimate expression of this is the merger of many states into a single state or ultimately into a single world government (Goldstein, 2003). It is further seen by Haas (1958) as the "process whereby political actors in several distinct national settings are persuaded to shift loyalties, expectations and political activities toward a new centre, whose institutions possess or demand jurisdiction over the pre-existing national states."

The integration theory is seen as having originated from functionalism. Functionalism according to Diego (2006) is a theory of international relations that arose principally from the experience of the Second World War and a strong concern about the obsolescence of the state as a form of social organization. Functionalists instead of agreeing with the realist view of self-interest of nation states as a motivating factor, rather focus on common interests and the needs shared by states and non-state actors in a process of global integration, triggered by the erosion of state sovereignty and the increasing weight of knowledge and hence of scientists and experts in the process of policy making. In the functionalism theory, international integration, the collective governance and interdependence

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between states develops its own internal dynamics as states integrate in limited functional, technical and economic areas. The functional theory was later modified by scholars to be able to explain developments in Europe. This is referred to as neo functionalism.

Neo functionalism argue that economic integration (functionalism) generates a political dynamic that drives integration further. Close economic ties require more political coordination in order to operate effectively and eventually lead to political integration as well- a process called spill over (Goldstein 2003). Sinnot (1993) believes the theory of integration has gone through three phases. These are Transnationalism and neo functionalism, a second short-lived phase characterized by an intense revisionism in the late 1960s and early 1970's and the third contemporary phase or revival. In the first phase, sense of community was an essential element, thus explaining why integration was defined as a matter of mutual consideration of partial identification in terms of semi-images and interests, of mutually successful predictions of behaviours and of cooperative actions in accordance with it (Deutsch 1957). The twelve conditions that were seen as essential to the process of integration include: mutual compatibility of main values; a distinctive way of life; we values, institutions and habits of action that mark the area off from major neighbours, unbroken links of social communication both across territories and across strata; broadening of political elite, both in regard to recruitment from wider strata and in regard to connections between strata, mobility of persons and a multiplicity of ranges of

communication and transition; and mutual predictability of behaviour (Sinnot 1993).

The neo functionalists on their own restricted the main motives for integration to integrationist elites, without according much weight or importance to public opinion. This led to the second phase which was revisionist, where a lot of importance was accorded public opinion in the process of integration, which (Sinnot, 1993) believes "the key concept in this regard and one of particular contemporary relevance is politicization" which involves "a broadening of the arena of participants, in which political legitimizing decision-makers and broad political opinion became more heavily involved as integration decisions make heavier] incursions upon national sovereignty and the identitive functions of the states".

The third phase which is quite recent involves different strands but also incorporates a core concern for public opinion especially in this era of democratization all over the world.

Methodology

The paper adopted mixed-method research design. The targeted population of the paper is 4,572 which comprises of individuals drawn from some selected staff of Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA), AU Secretariat in Nigeria, National Electoral Commission (INEC), Independent Corrupt Practices Commission and Economic and Financial Crimes Commission; form a vital part of the population. These groups were carefully chosen because they are positioned at the intersection of political development affairs, community engagement, and socio-

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economic planning, offering crucial perspectives relevant to the paper's objectives. Using the Krejcie & Morgan (1970) statistical method of sample size determination, the sample size of the paper is derived at three hundred and fifty four (354).

The paper employed both primary and secondary methods of data collection. The instruments that were used in collecting data for this paper are oral interview questionnaires and secondary sources. Stratified and Random Sampling Techniques were used in selecting the respondents among different categories for the administration of questionnaire. For interview, purposive sampling technique was used. The sampling comprised of people with many similar characteristics such as deep knowledge on the subject of investigation, years of experience and age. This paper made use of charts as a platform to present the research data and also analyze the data collected from the field on the subject matter using simple percentage and graphs as the case may be for the descriptive analysis. The version that was used for analyzing data for the paper is SPSS 25. Content analysis was used to analyze qualitative information.

Data Analysis and Interpretation of Results

A total of 342 copies of questionnaire were distributed while 325 copies were retrieved. Therefore, the presentation and analysis was done based on the 325 retrieved copies of questionnaire. The pattern of presentation was based on the objectives of the paper using charts (pie and bar charts). 12 KII responses were collated, transcribed, coded and analyzed. The

discussion of findings then followed. This was supported with information from extant literature.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Role of African Union in Promoting Good Governance in Nigeria

The first research question was to determine the role of role of African union in promoting good governance in Nigeria. To address this research question, the paper asked respondents appropriate questions. The data generated are presented in Figures 1 to 3.

Figure 1: Respondents view on the Assessment of whether or not African Union Effectively Collaborates with Nigerian Government Institutions to Promote Good Governance in the Country.

Source: Author's Field Survey (2024)

The analysis in Figure 1 shows that majority of respondents cumulatively ranking 297 (91.4 per cent) respondents assessed the role of African Union effectively collaborates with Nigerian government institutions to promote good governance in the country. Only 8.6 per cent of respondents cumulatively opined that African Union effectively collaborates with Nigerian government institutions to promote good governance in the country. It could be surmised from the analysis that the African Union has aided in effectively collaborating with

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Nigerian government institutions to promote good governance in the country. Hence, the need for Nigeria to always paved way and provide a solid ground for smooth running and execution of African Union policies, programmes and initiatives in order to promote good governance and encourage political development in the country.

In a KII (3/01/24) with Assistant Principal Officer, Election and Monitoring Unit, INEC, Abuja, he averred that yes, African union effectively collaborates with Nigerian government and institutions such as INEC in order to ensure free fair and credible election as well as good governance.

On the other hand an Executive Officer Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Abuja, opined in a KII (4/01/24) that yes, the African Union effectively collaborates with Nigerian government institutions to promote good governance in the country through its policies and programmes like the electoral observer missions, the anticorruption programmes, the campaign for human rights, etc.

In the same vein, Director Voter Registry INEC, Abuja, submitted in a KII (3/01/24) that the organization (African Union) assist in terms of security and other matters that will promote good governance.

According to a Deputy Director African Union Division Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Abuja, (4/01/24), he opined that Nigeria Collaborates with the African union to achieve its goals especially agenda 2063 to ensure good governance and democracy as well as human right and rule of law.

In another interview a Principal Administrative Officer, EFCC, Abuja,

opined in a KII (5/01/24) that the Nigerian government has been part of the union from its formation, it has promoted unity amongst states, Nigerian state had benefitted from trades, economic values and bilateral relation.

Figure 2: Respondents view Ascertaining African Union Supports Capacity Building Initiatives to Enhance Good Governance in Nigeria.

Source: Author's Field Survey (2024).

The analysis in Figure 2 shows that majority of respondents cumulatively ranking 84 per cent respondents ascertained that the African Union supports capacity building initiatives to enhance good governance in Nigeria. Only 16 per cent of respondents cumulatively disagreed that African Union supports capacity building initiatives to enhance good governance in Nigeria. It could be surmised from the analysis that indeed African Union has on various occasion embarked on capacity building initiatives to enhance good governance in Nigeria.

Figure 3: Respondents view on African Union's Strategies and Programs have Effectively Strengthened Transparency and Accountability in Nigerian Governance Structures.

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Source: Author’s Field Survey (2024).

The analysis in Figure 3 shows that an overwhelming majority of respondents making up 56.9 per cent (185) of respondents agreed by opining that African Union's strategies and programs have effectively strengthened transparency and accountability in Nigerian governance structures. Whereas 5.8 percent (19) strongly agreed with the posed question. However, only 37.3 per cent (121 respondents) cumulatively disagreed with the posed question. This implies that there is need to solidify, strengthen and sustain African Union's strategies and programs in order effectively strengthened transparency and accountability in Nigerian governance structures.

In corroborating the forgoing analysis, an executive officer Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Abuja, averred in a KII (4/01/24) that the African Union's strategies and programs have not effectively strengthened transparency and accountability in Nigerian governance structures hence, the need to improve it a bit.

On the other hand, Director Voter Registry INEC, Abuja confirmed in a KII (3/01/24) that the African union through collaboration with other agencies contributed greatly in bringing transparency and

accountability in the governance of Nigeria.

In the same vein a Deputy Director AU Division MFA, Abuja, averred in a KII (4/01/24) that yes, the African union has effectively strengthened the institutions responsible for transparency and accountability in Nigeria by supporting the EFCC, ICPC, Transparency International Code of Conduct Bureau etc. as well as implementing the AU convention on anti-corruption.

In another interview conducted with Principal Administrative Officer INEC, Abuja, (3/01/24), he stated that his opinion is perceived on that the idea behind its formation is yet to be attained the unity is in disarray mainly due to political and economic instability. However, Nigeria is steadily achieving its objectives.

Figure 4: Respondents view on the African Union has Successfully Implemented Initiatives or Projects that have Significantly Contributed to Improving Governance Practices in Nigeria.

Source: Author’s Field Survey (2024).

The responses contained in Figure 4 revealed that 113 (34.8 per cent) and 19 (5.8 percent) respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that African Union has successfully

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implemented initiatives or projects that have significantly contributed to improving governance practices in Nigeria. Another category of respondents ranking 185 (56.9 per cent) and 8 (2.5 percent) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively by opining that African Union did not successfully implemented initiatives or projects and have not significantly contributed to improving governance practices in Nigeria.

In respect to the forgoing response and an analysis from the questionnaire above, the Assistant Principal Officer, Election and Monitoring Unit, INEC, Abuja, confirmed in a KII (3/01/24) that Yes, the African Union has successfully implemented initiatives or projects that have significantly contributed to improving governance practices in Nigeria through stabilization programmes in returning democratic values in some African countries such as Niger Republic, Chad Republic among others which is still ongoing.

Whereas an Executive Officer Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Abuja averred in a KII (4/01/24), that some of the protocols and charters of the African Union to which Nigeria is a party to has helped improved governance.

In the same vein a Deputy Director AU Division MFA, Abuja, (4/01/23) is of the opinion that yes, the African union through AUDA-NEPAD has being implementing projects and coordinating MDA's to effectively enhance good governance, Nigeria has completed its second peer review and submitted it country report as at 2023. All programs of MDA's are geared towards achieving the goals and aspirations of agenda 2023 of the African union.

A Principal Administrative Officer from EFCC, Abuja, submitted in a KII (5/01/24) that to some extent yes, and reason is one of the African objectives is to sustain democracy across member states and Nigeria has gradually made the transition and on the verge of ensuring it credibility and sustainability.

The analysis infers that the Nigerian government need to emplace institutional mechanisms in addressing the loopholes in its democratic practice and protection of human right as well as in other African countries and beyond in order to ensure that the globe is safe and free for everyone to do what they deem fit in accordance to the provisions of the laid down rules and regulations of the state and international system and to promote political development in the country.

Impacts African Union Policies and Initiatives have on the Fight against Corruption in Nigeria

The second research question was to determine the impact African Union policies and initiatives have on the fight against corruption in Nigeria. To address this research question, the paper asked respondents appropriate questions. The data generated are presented from figure 5 to 7.

Figure 5: Respondents view on Whether African Union Policies and Initiatives have a Significant Impact on the Fight against Corruption in Nigeria.

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Source: Author's Field Survey (2024).

The responses contained in Figure 5 shows that cumulatively 63 per cent of respondents were of the view that African Union policies and initiatives have a significant impact on the fight against corruption in Nigeria. Only a cumulative of 37 per cent of respondents opined by disagreeing with the assertion that African Union policies and initiatives have a significant impact on the fight against corruption in Nigeria.

In corroborating the forgoing analysis, the Executive Officer Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Abuja, averred in a KII (4/01/24) that there is a convention that was signed by Nigeria and members of the African Union which is the African convention on preventing and combating corruption in Africa which has to some extent aided in the fight against corruption in Nigeria.

On the other hand, a Director Voter Registry INEC, Abuja, submitted in a KII (3/01/24) that African Union in conjunction with other development patterns has a great impact in fighting corruption in Nigeria.

In the same vein, a Deputy Director AU Division MFA, Abuja, observed in a KII (4/01/24) that the African Union's board for anti-corruption monitors the various institution of anti-corruption in Nigeria and a robust reporting system from Nigeria's agencies to the AUBAC is maintained

annually. This keeps Nigeria's anti-corruption agencies on it toes.

In another interview, a Principal Administrative Officer EFCC, Abuja, observed in a KII (5/01/24) that despite the formation of inter-governmental action group against laundering in west only but small had been achieved due to our porous security system in Nigeria.

On the other hand, a Principal Administrative Officer INEC, Abuja, (3/01/24) averred that, the AU anti-corruption impact on Nigeria has to do with the discouragement on bribery domestic or foreign, diversion of public property as regard to Nigeria and other countries in Africa.

Figure 6: Respondents view Ascertaining whether African Union's Policies and Initiatives Effectively Address the Root Causes of Corruption in Nigeria.

Source: Author's Field Survey (2024).

Figure 6 above depicts that, 119 respondents representing 43 per cent cumulatively opined that the African Union's policies and initiatives effectively address the root causes of corruption in Nigeria. In addition, 52 per cent and 11 per cent of respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed that African Union's policies and initiatives

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effectively address the root causes of corruption in Nigeria.

It is, therefore, imperative for the Nigerian government and stakeholders involved to ensure that their actions and inactions towards fighting and addressing the root causes of corruption are in tandem with the ideas and initiatives of African Union in the fight against corruption especially the resolution of the African Union Convention on Preventing and Combating Corruption (AUCPCC) as well as the AU Agenda 2063.

Figure 7: Respondents view the African Union Actively Collaborates with Nigerian Government Institutions to Combat Corruption in the Country.

Source: Author's Field Survey (2024).

The responses on Figure 7 depicts that a cumulative of 265 (81.5 per cent) respondents were of the view that the African Union actively collaborates with Nigerian government institutions to combat corruption in the country. Another category of respondents ranking 60 (18.5 per cent) respondents cumulatively disagreed that the African Union actively collaborates with Nigerian government institutions to combat corruption in the country.

In respect to the forgoing analysis, an Executive Officer Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Abuja, submitted in a KII

(4/01/24), that yes, African Union actively collaborates with Nigerian government institutions to combat corruption in the country. This is done through a department in the African Union called the African Union advisory board against corruption and Nigerian institutions like EFCC, ICPC, and PACAC.

On the other hand, a Director Voter Registry INEC, Abuja, opined in a KII (3/01/24) that yes, the African Union is participating in activities with the government institution to combat corruption in Nigeria.

In the same vein a Deputy Director AU Division MFA, Abuja, averred in a KII (4/01/24), that yes, the African union board for anti-corruption collaborates with the anti-corruption agencies in Nigeria, in 2022. Nigeria's president Muhammadu Buhari was named Africa's champion for Anti-corruption.

In another interview, a Principal Administrative Officer INEC, Abuja, observed in a KII (3/01/24) that the union anti-corruption policies are only by paper and rhetoric whenever there is a meeting but the objectives had always been a mere statement.

Findings and Discussion

Role of African Union in Promoting Good Governance in Nigeria

The paper found that the African Union effectively collaborates with Nigerian government institutions to promote good governance in the country through its policies and programmes like the electoral observer missions (AUEOM), the anticorruption programmes, the campaign for human rights, among others. In corroborating the above finding, it was averred by Mangu (2014) that democracy and good

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political governance are prominently mentioned in the AU Constitutive Act and are the first thematic areas under the African Peer-Review Mechanism (APRM), through which AU has undoubtedly made substantial efforts to promote democracy. AU also enacted a number of other instruments, including the African Charter for Democracy, Elections, and Governance (ACDEG) to encourage democracy and sound political governance among its member states.

The paper further discovered that the African union has effectively strengthened the institutions responsible for transparency and accountability in Nigeria by supporting the EFCC, ICPC, Transparency International and Code of Conduct Bureau among others. As well as implementing the AU convention on anti-corruption. AU's persistence and demand for better democratic governance, including peaceful and credible transfers of power, anti-corruption department, transparent and accountable exercise of power, the progressive realization of the fundamental rights and freedoms enshrined in national and international legal frameworks, are causing a significant number of African countries to democratize against all odds (Aniekwe, Oette & Vandeginste, 2019). Also, AU's African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance (ACDEG), which was established in 2007, requires state parties to establish and strengthen democratic institutions, the rule of law, human rights and independent electoral systems (Kioko, 2019).

Furthermore, the paper observed that the African union through AUDA-

NEPAD has been implementing projects and coordinating MDA's to effectively enhance good governance, Nigeria has completed its second peer review and submitted its country report as at 2023. All programs of MDA's are geared towards achieving the goals and aspirations of agenda 2023 of the African Union. Many African countries have made significant progress toward establishing stable and accountable multiparty democratic systems as a result of AU's and other African regional organisations' focused engagement in defending democracy (Campbell & Quinn, 2021).

Impact of African Union Policies and Initiatives have on the Fight against Corruption in Nigeria

The paper discovered that the African Union's board for anti-corruption monitors the various institution of anti-corruption in Nigeria and a robust reporting system from Nigeria's agencies to the AUBAC is maintained annually. This keeps Nigeria's anti-corruption agencies on it toes. It is not surprising that the AU has continued to promote anti-corruption programmes among its member states, having acknowledged that the maintenance of democracy in Africa would be challenging without significant reduction in governance corruption. In order to tackle the pervasive corruption on the African continent, AU enacted the African Union Convention on Preventing and Combating Corruption (AUCPCC) in 2003 (Ayodeji, Kolade & Abiodun, 2023). The paper further unveiled that African Union actively collaborates with Nigerian government institutions to combat corruption in the country. This

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is done through a department in the African Union called the African Union advisory board against corruption and Nigerian institutions like EFCC, ICPC, and PACAC. The AUCPCC vis-à-vis the African Union Advisory Board on Corruption (AUABC) has been assisting in the enforcement and implementation of anti-corruption measures, African Peer Review Mechanism (APRM), the 2018 African Anti-Corruption Year, who are the flagbearers of the AU anti-corruption initiatives (Action Aid Nigeria, 2019; Campbell & Quinn, 2021).

AU established the African Union Advisory Board on Corruption (AUABC) in 2009 as an autonomous organ in accordance with Article 22 of the convention to ensure that the AU convention was properly implemented. In order to prevent, detect, punish, and eradicate corruption and related offenses in Africa, it is crucial that state parties to the AUCPCC adopt measures and actions (Duri, 2020).

Conclusion

The paper examines African Union's efforts to promote political development in Nigeria and how they have affected its anti-corruption initiatives, good governance, democratic consolidation and the challenges faced by the union. It acknowledges that AU's commitment to advancing political development in Nigeria through its various frameworks has brought about some progress. However, the organisation's anti-corruption initiatives have clearly not effectively reflected its measures. As a result, despite minor improvements in various corruption perception indices reported by TI and other associated global anti-corruption organisations, corruption persists in

many member countries and Nigeria in particular. Hence, a lack of common democratic ideals and the fact that Nigeria is failing to uphold its obligations under the AU's anti-corruption convention have all served to limit and undermine AU's effort in ensuring political development within and beyond Nigeria. Thus, lack of implementation drive, and insufficient resources are just a few of the major challenges confronting AU's anti-corruption initiatives on money laundering, illicit enrichment, political party funding, lack of expertise and tools, bad governance and limited autonomy of justice authorities.

Recommendations

- i. Nigerian government, Economic and Financial Crime Commission, Independent Corrupt Practices Commission and Code of Conduct Bureau should as a matter of urgency endeavor to implement the African Union Convention on Preventing and Combating Corruption (AUCPCC) resolution in order to effectively combat corruption in the country.
- ii. The Nigerian government needs to put into cognizance the reports of AUEOM observers in order to improve quality and credibility of elections in the country.

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